

Supplementary material for

Enhancing the Learning of Database Access Programming using Continuous Integration and Aspect Oriented Programming

Students and Teachers' Workflow per Assignment

In this document, we describe the general workflow we propose to improve the distribution, handing in and grading of assignments. We rely on Figure 1 to illustrate our explanations.

Figure 1. Workflow per assignment

Having defined an assignment with the template repository, GitHub Classroom allows instructors to send out an invitation to students, which, when accepted, will automatically setup a new private repository in GitHub for that student for the current assignment. The students can easily clone the repository in their usual IDE (such as Eclipse) to start coding and run integration tests.

Each time a student runs an integration test, BPs are also automatically checked for compliance by using our AOP module. Both the tests and the AOP module are used as a self-evaluation tool to check which test has passed/failed and at what extent BPs have been implemented, displaying the corresponding feedback report (see Figure 2). The student can work on her/his assignment either until it is completed (all test pass and BPs are implemented) or until the due date for the assignment. We thus help students by providing feedback on their work and let them improve it accordingly. This also reduces the assessment workload of the teacher, since students do the assessment work at least partly by themselves.

Figure 2. Eclipse IDE showing test results and AOP report

At any moment during the development of the assignment and, in particular, when the student wants to hand in the assignment, she/he can decide to push the code to her/his GitHub repository to be accessible via the web. GitHub will automatically notify Travis of the change, which in turn, will clone the repository and automatically run the configured integration tests (together with the AOP module). Whenever students want, they can also check Travis feedback through the corresponding Travis' URL. Travis feedback includes, in addition to the information displayed in the Eclipse console (SEE Figure 3), the build status using the green colour, if all tests pass, and red, otherwise (see Figure 4).

Figure 3. Travis feedback with tests results and AOP report.

Figure 4. Travis Green signal

At any time, teachers can access Travis to easily check the correctness of a student's build by consulting Travis feedback. Then, they can grade the student's work or they can also access the Git repository of the assignment to revise the code, if desired. Based on this information, they can easily grade the student's assignment. When wanted to provide a detailed feedback (for example when the student asks for help), the teacher can pull the student's repository from Eclipse, run all the tests, inspect the code, and give her/his comments of praise, criticism or advice to the student.

This way of working allows creating a real-time feedback loop between instructor and students for coding exercises, as well as streamline the management process and grading of deliveries.